

Synthesis of *N*¹-(2-Pyridinecarbonyl)-3-methyl-4-(substituted-hydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-one[†]

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2-Pyridinecarboxylic acid hydrazide and their derivatives are generally used as antibacterial agent. *N*¹-(2-Pyridinecarbonyl)-3-methyl-4-(substituted hydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-one and their derivatives have been synthesised. Their R_f values, chemical analysis, ir and nmr spectra are recorded.

THE chemistry¹ and wide range of pharmaceutical properties of 2-pyrazolin-5-one derivatives, like germicides², antimicrobial agents³, antiactinics⁴, antidiuretics⁵, analgesics and antipyretics⁶, antifungals⁷, antihistaminics⁸, anti-*M. tuberculosis*⁹, antirheumatics¹⁰, antibacterial¹¹, and similar such diseases have been cited in literature. Sulphadruugs are well known chemotherapeutic agent. 2-Pyridinecarboxylic acid hydrazide^{12,13} and their derivatives are generally used as antibacterial agent.

The present paper deals that when diazotised sulphadruugs, aromatic amines are condensed at reactive methylene position of β -ketoesters, sulpha/substituted phenylhydrazono-ethyl-2,3-dioxobutyrate¹⁴ are obtained. The condensed product on cyclisation with 2-pyridinecarboxylic acid hydrazide gives *N*¹-(2-pyridinecarbonyl)-3-methyl-4-(substituted hydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-one, and their biological activity was studied.

Experimental

Ir spectra (nujol, KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 621 grading ir spectrophotometer. The compounds were analysed for nitrogen on Coleman analyser and data found were well in agreement, within limits of the possible experimental error, with the calculated values. The homogeneity and purity of the compounds were tested through tlc.

*N*¹-(2-Pyridinecarbonyl)-3-methyl-4-(*X*) hydrazono-2-pyrazolin-5-one: 2-Pyridinecarboxylic acid hydrazide (0.005 mol) and sulpha/substituted phenylhydrazono-ethyl-2,3-dioxobutyrate (0.005 mol) were

dissolved in sufficient quantity of glacial acetic acid and contents were refluxed on a water-bath for 3 h. On cooling, a coloured solid compound separated out was filtered, dried and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid/DMF.

By adopting similar procedure, a few substituted-2-pyrazolin-5-ones have been synthesised and their characteristics are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF *N*¹-(2-PYRIDINECARBO-NYL)-3-METHYL-4-(X)-HYDRAZONO-2-PYRAZOLIN-5-ONE*

Sl. no.	X	M.p. °C	Colour*
1.	3-Chlorophenyl	185	DY
2.	4-Chlorophenyl	212	PY
3.	2-Methoxyphenyl	227	O
4.	3-Methoxyphenyl	155	RB
5.	4-Methoxyphenyl	197	SDO
6.	2-Methylphenyl	220	SDOF
7.	4-Methylphenyl	192	SON
8.	3-Nitro, 4-methylphenyl	225	DY
9.	4-Aminodiaryl	248	SLBN
10.	2-Chloro, 4-nitrophenyl	238 d	PY
11.	2,4,6-Tribromophenyl	202	BY
12.	<i>N</i> -Aceto-4-aminophenyl	230	B
13.	1-Naphthyl	257	SLBN
14.	2-Naphthyl	245	SDEN
15.	2-Sulphanilamidobenzene	248	SOP
16.	<i>N</i> ¹ -2-Pyridylsulphanilamidobenzene	245	DY
17.	<i>N</i> ¹ -2-Thiazolyl sulphanilamido-benzene	243	LO
18.	<i>N</i> ¹ -2-Pyrimidyl sulphanilamido-benzene	249	DY
19.	<i>N</i> ¹ -2-Guanyl sulphanilamidobenzene	250	DeY
20.	<i>N</i> ¹ -2-Acetyl sulphanilamidobenzene	230	PY
21.	<i>N</i> ¹ -2-(4,6-Dimethyl)-pyrimidyl-sulphanilamidobenzene	255	LY
22.	<i>N</i> ¹ -2-Quinoxalyl sulphanilamido-benzene	172	B
23.	2,3-Dimethyl-1-phenylpyrazolone	210	SPeN
24.	4-Carboxyl phenyl	245	PY

* Elemental analyses of compounds found satisfactory, yield between 70 to 85%.

** D=Dark, De=dull, P=pale, Y=yellow, Pe=pink, S=shining, N=needles, B=brown, F=flakes, R=red, O=orange, L=light.

d=Decomposed.

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Ir spectra : The spectra had characteristic peaks at 780 (aromatic ring), 1520 (C=C-NH-N), 1741 (C=O) amide, 1672 (C=O) cyclic, 1613 (C=N), 1560 (heterocyclic five membered 2-pyrazolin-5-one ring) and 1480 cm⁻¹ (six membered heterocyclic pyridine ring).

Nmr spectra : The structure of 2-pyrazolin-5-ones were also confirmed by nmr spectra studies.

2-Pyrazolin-5-one : δ (CDCl₃) 2.48 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.07-7.84 (8H, m, aromatic) (two) and 8.13-8.24 (1H, NH).

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